

IMPACT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS ON SELF ESTEEM OF THE ASPIRANTS FOR PREPARING OF COMPETITIVE EXAMINATION

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ABSTRACT:

This study aims to investigate the impact of Self Esteem Aspirants for Preparing of Competitive Examination. Self-esteem affects the enjoyment of life even if it does not have a substantial impact on career success, productivity, or other objective outcome measures. Given the choice, however, most people would prefer to have high self-esteem. That self-esteem is vital for psychological health is evident in the popular media and in educational policy. The sample of the present study consisted of 300 (150 High Socio-Economic Status, and 150 Low Socio-Economic Status) aspirants from different locality of Ranchi, Jharkhand. This study was used stratified random sampling technique and samples were done by using self Esteem inventory Cooper Smith (1967). Result showed that Socio-Economic status play significant role in the self Esteem among High socio-Economic status and Low socio-Economic status aspirants. Low socio-economic status experiences significantly High self Esteem than the High Socio-Economic status aspirants.

KEYWORDS:

SELF -ESTEEM, ASPIRANTS, INSTITUTE, IMPACT, SOCIO-ECONOMIC.

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

27th September 2025

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

30th September 2025

INTRODUCTION

Self-Esteem is meant more than an innate sense of self-worth that presumably is a human birthright. Self-Esteem is individuals' experience that they are appropriate to life and to the requirements of life. More specifically, self-esteem is confidence in the ability to think; confidence in the ability to cope with the challenges of life; and confidence in the right to be happy, the feeling of being worthy, deserving, entitled to assert one's needs and wants and to enjoy the fruits of one's efforts. Self-Esteem is not a free gift, but a possession over time which represents an achievement. To say that self-esteem is a basic human need is to say that it makes an essential contribution to the life process; that it is indispensable to normal and healthy development; and that it has survival-value. If individuals do not believe in themselves the universe is a frightening place. The change from a manufacturing society to an information society and other social changes create demands for higher levels of education and training than were required of previous generations. These developments also create new demands on psychological resources. Persons possessing a decent level of self-esteem are now needed economically in large numbers. The virtues that self-esteem asks of individuals are also ones that life asks of individuals.

A [2019 study](#) found that low self-esteem in students had a significant impact on their quality of life. Researchers

found that low self-esteem had an association with anxiety, depression, academic stress, and thoughts self-esteem is meant more than an innate sense of self-worth that presumably is a human birthright. Self-esteem is individuals' experience that they are appropriate to life and to the requirements of life. More specifically, self-esteem is confidence in the ability to think

METHODOLOGY

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

- To proposed to assess the level of Self Esteem of the aspirants for preparing competitive examination

HYPOTHESIS

There will be significant differences between high low socio-economic status on self esteem of the aspirants for preparing of competitive examination

SAMPLE

Sample size (300) 150 high socio-economic status and 150 low socio-economic status of the study: The present study aim to determined to assess the level of Self Esteem of the aspirants for preparing competitive examination of the students healing from Ranchi District. The problem for the investigation has been A Study of Self Esteem among

aspirants for preparing competitive examination.

Inclusion criteria: All participant are preparing competitive examination, Participant ranged between the ages of 21 to 35 years, Educated up to BA and MA, Religion of Hindu, Muslim, and Christian, Gender Male and Female and all participant has been selected for only Ranchi District. **Exclusion Criteria:** Below 12th standard Aspirants, below age range of 20 years and above 35 years, and out of Ranchi Jharkhand

TOOL USED

Cooper smith Self-esteem inventories The cooper smith self-stem inventory was developed by Cooper Smith (1967) to assess a broad range of self esteem it consists of 57 items and measures 6 areas of self esteem, general self, social, self-peers, home-parents, school academic, reliability estimates were calculated. Obtained coefficients are .81 for grade .86 for grade 9 and .80 for grade 12. The coefficients indicate adequate internal consistency for students in three grades.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

TABLE -1 MEAN SCORE OF HIGH AND LOW SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS ASPIRANTS OF COMPETITIVE EXAMINATION ON SELF ESTEEM

GROUP	N	Mean	SD	t	Df	Significant
HIGH SES	150	39.2	4.7	2.8	298	.01
LOW SES	150	40.6	4.4			

Table 1. Shows that N, Mean and SD score of high Socio-Economic Status aspirants were 150 & 39.2 and 4.7 respectively. Mean and SD score of low Socio-Economic Status aspirants were 150 & 40.6 and 4.4 respectively. The t value between two groups (high SES aspirants and low SES aspirants While N) was found 't'= 2.08 which shows there was statistically significant difference between two groups (df =298, p =0.01). The result indicates that low socio-economic aspirants' status having high self esteem and high socio-economic status aspirants having low self esteem.

CONCLUSION

The study shows that low socio-economic aspirants status having high Self Esteem and high socio-economic aspirants status having low Self esteem. The present study have been supported by the previous study by Mustapha N. 1997.

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